

EFFECT OF HEALTH AND EDUCATION ON LABOUR PRODUCTIVITY IN NIGERIA (1999-2024)

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17630127>

Abstract: This study focused on the effect of health and education on labour productivity in Nigeria between the time frame of 1999-2024. The study is guided by the following specific objectives; to determine the impact of health and education on labour productivity in Nigeria, to examine the causality relationship between health and education on labour productivity in Nigeria. The research design adopted is the Ex Post Facto. The Ex Post Facto design was used because the study is a quasi-experimental study examining how independent variables affect a dependent variable. This study build a multiple regression model and make use of econometrics procedure in estimating the relationship between my economic variables. Real gross domestic product is dependent variable whereas government expenditure in education and government expenditure on health are the independent variables. The findings of the study reveals that health and government education expenditure both has positive relationships with Real Gross Domestic Product over the period covered, it implies that an increase in the values of government expenditure on health and government education expenditure will lead to an increase in the economic growth of Nigeria. More so, the granger causality result indicates a unidirectional causality relationship flowing from government education expenditure exists between government education expenditure and Real Gross Domestic Product, a bidirectional causality relationship exists between government expenditure on health and Real Gross Domestic Product. The study recommends that government and its education and health agencies should as well reach out to rural communities in a bid to provide educational and health facilities for the dwellers of such places which will increase the human capital of the country and hence the economic growth of Nigeria.

Key Words: Government expenditure on Health, Government expenditure on Education expenditure, Labour productivity.

INTRODUCTION

Health and education are two closely related human capital components that work together to make the individual more productive. Taking one component as more important than the other is unrealistic as an educated individual who is ill is as inefficient as an illiterate (Bakre, 2021). Both components are thus related together because of their close relationship. Appleton and Teal (1998), describe health and education as components of human capital that are contributors to human welfare. They describe these components as different from other types of goods

produced in societies. While high incomes may be conducive to health it cannot be directly purchased like material goods and services. Health and education are often subsidized by the state and in some countries, education is compulsory for certain minimum length of time. Nigeria, which was one of the richest 50 countries in the early 1970s, has retrogressed to become one of the 25 poorest counties at threshold of the twenty-first century. The belief in human capital as a necessity for growth started in Nigeria during the implementation of the 1955-60 development plans and today, with the importance of knowledge in the economy, human capital has increasingly attracted both academic and public interest (Ezeh, 2024).

The importance of investing in education and health is well appreciated and understood in economies that wish to attain sustainable growth. Nigeria is rated by international standards as 'less developed' and thus has economic growth as a major goal. Indeed, the importance of a prime sector such as education has been stressed in Nigeria since the early sixties following the submission of the Ashby report in September 1960. In recent times, during a keynote address by the former governor of the Central Bank - Dr J.O Sanusi (2002), he stressed the importance of human capital development for Nigeria, saying that the Nigerian economy has to be efficient and competitive in the new world order in which national frontiers no longer constitute barriers to human, material, and capital flows. He noted that one of the greatest barriers facing Nigeria in this millennium is the issue of capacity building to enhance productivity in the economy. This can be attained through investment in the human capital sector of the economy (Ezeh, 2024).

Over the last three decades researchers and policy makers have increasingly recognised health as a form of human capital that directly affects workers' ability to supply labour, the quality of that labour, and overall economic output. Poor health reduces work effort, increases absenteeism and presenteeism (working while sick), and shortens productive working lives all channels through which population health can lower labour productivity and aggregate growth. Nigeria faces a heavy and complex health burden that weakens its labour force. Indicators such as high maternal and under-five mortality, relatively low life expectancy and the continuing prevalence of infectious diseases (malaria, HIV/TB) combine with rising non-communicable diseases to reduce healthy working years and increase lost work days. These health challenges occur alongside low public health spending and large out-of-pocket payments, which together limit access to effective care and amplify the productivity costs of illness.

Health financing in Nigeria is heavily reliant on private and out-of-pocket spending: multiple country assessments show that household out-of-pocket payments account for a very large share of total health expenditure (well above 60–70% in many years), while government health spending as a share of GDP has remained low. This financing profile both reflects and reinforces weak access to timely care, with implications for worker absenteeism, poorer recovery from illness, and chronic loss of productive capacity.

Despite the growing literature, gaps remain. Many existing studies use aggregate national time-series data or single health indicators; relatively few combine sectoral or firm-level measures of worker health and productivity in Nigeria, and fewer still investigate short-run (absenteeism/presenteeism) versus long-run (health capital, life expectancy) channels simultaneously. Additionally, policy reforms (e.g., recent World Bank and multilateral

health financing initiatives) and evolving disease patterns mean updated empirical work using recent data is needed to inform current policy choices.

Statement of the Problem

Labour productivity is one of the most critical determinants of economic growth and national competitiveness. In Nigeria, however, labour productivity has remained persistently low despite the country's abundant human and natural resources (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2023). One major factor attributed to this situation is the poor state of health among the working population. A large proportion of Nigerian workers suffer from preventable diseases such as malaria, typhoid, and hypertension, which reduce their physical strength, concentration, and efficiency at work (World Health Organization [WHO], 2022). Poor health also increases absenteeism and presenteeism, leading to significant loss of productive time and reduced overall output.

Despite the recognized link between health and productivity, Nigeria continues to experience low investment in health infrastructure and services. Government expenditure on health remains below the 15% benchmark recommended by the Abuja Declaration, while out-of-pocket health spending exceeds 70% of total health expenditure (World Bank, 2022). This situation leaves many workers unable to access quality healthcare when ill, resulting in prolonged sickness and reduced productivity. The weak healthcare delivery system, coupled with inadequate health insurance coverage, further compounds the problem, especially among informal sector workers who constitute the majority of Nigeria's labour force.

Empirical studies in other developing countries have consistently shown that improved health outcomes significantly enhance workers' productivity and overall economic performance (Bloom & Canning, 2019). However, in Nigeria, the extent to which health status affects labour productivity remains underexplored and inadequately documented. Many existing studies either focus on health expenditure and economic growth or examine productivity from a purely macroeconomic perspective without isolating the specific contribution of health variables. Consequently, there is insufficient empirical evidence to guide policy interventions aimed at improving workers' health as a means of enhancing productivity.

Therefore, the central problem this study seeks to address is the inadequate understanding of how health conditions, healthcare access, and public health investments influence labour productivity in Nigeria. Without empirical evidence on this relationship, policymakers may continue to overlook health as a strategic component of labour productivity and economic growth.

Objective of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine the effect of health on labour productivity in Nigeria. This study shall be guided by the following specific objectives objectives

1. To determine the impact of health and education on labour productivity in Nigeria.
2. To examine the causality relationship between health and education on labour productivity in Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions;

1. What is the impact of health and education on labour productivity in Nigeria?

2. What is the causality relationship between health and education on labour productivity in Nigeria?

Hypotheses of the Study

1. H_{01} : Health and education have no significant impact on labour productivity in Nigeria
2. H_{02} : Health and education have no causality relationship on labour productivity in Nigeria

Scope of the Study

This study seeks to determine the effect of health on labour productivity in Nigeria between the time frame 1999-2024. The study will be limited to Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Concept of Human Capital Development

To understand the concept of human capital development, it is of importance that we understand the meaning of capital. According to A. W. Lewis in “Economic Development with Unlimited Supplies of Labour” Capital refers to already produced durable goods which further contribute to the production of goods and services. In simpler words, capital refers to any produced good/service which enables an individual/organization to deliver high quality output. Capital acts as a catalyst to increase productivity in organizations.

Human capital is a term popularized by Gary Becker, an economist from university of Chicago and Jacob Mincer that refers to the stock of competencies, knowledge and personality attributes embodied in the ability to perform labour so as to produce economic value. It is the attributes gained by a worker through education and experience (K.K Ghai, 2017). Human capital formation is the process of adding to stock of human capital over time. It is possible through creation of skilled, trained and efficient labour force by providing better education, health, care facilities, etc. Thus, it is a process of providing education, healthcare facilities, research and training facilities to the labour force so that they can handle the sophisticated capital equipment’s efficiently and can innovate new ideas and methods of production through their enhanced knowledge (K.K Ghai, 2017).

Human Capital is a measure of the skills, education, capacity and attributes of labour which influence their productive capacity and earning potential (Tejvan Pettinger, 2017). According to the OECD, human capital is defined as the knowledge, skills, competencies and other attributes embodied in individuals or groups of individuals acquired during their life and used to produce goods, services or ideas in market circumstances”. Individual human capital is the skills and abilities of individual workers Human capital of the economy. The aggregate human capital of an economy, which will be determined by national educational standards. For statistical purposes, human capital can be measured in monetary terms as the total potential future earnings of the working age population (Tejvan Pettinger, 2017).

Concept of Productivity

Productivity: Productivity is an index which is used to measure the ratio of output per unit of input (Imaga, 2019). It simply tells whether or not factors of production are contributing more or less total output. Yusuf (2022) defined productivity as the ratio between output and all the resources used in production i.e. capital, labour, raw materials etc. the most efficient use of all available resources. Tunde (2022) defined productivity as the “achievement of

desired output coupled with a maximum utilization of resources which includes man, money, material and machinery.” He further argued that, in order to increase productivity of our country, slashing of wages of workers in order to match productivity. The author also said that since our economy is labour intensive, emphasis should be designed to suit the economy. Terba (2022) pointed out that productivity of labour in industry depends not only on the quality and quantity of labour used, but also on the quality and quality of their inputs that are cooperate with labour. According to Saasongu (2025), defined productivity as all those activities which cover all the physical and mental efforts that satisfy human wants.

Factors Responsible for Low Productivity of Nigerian Workers

In the course of this study, the paper observed the following as some of the factors responsible for low productivity of Nigerian workers in public sector as follows:

(1) Poor Educational Background of Workers: Most of the staff of Nigerian workers in public sector have discovered to be lacking in terms of their educational background, majority of them had the certificates without the basic knowledge, instruction, abilities required of their jobs. Consequently, most of them find it very difficult to steer the affairs of their various positions thereby creating lapses here and there which should not have been.

(2) Lack of Training: As rightly defined by Denyer (2019), “training is the adoption or moulding of a person to increase his fitness for a specific activity. Training of workers would make them more productive as well as improve their morale, thereby increasing their loyalty and adaptability of their immediate environment. According to Saasongu (2025), training involves the inculcation, learning and development of skills, knowledge and values required by employees to effectively perform tasks for the organization. It is a conscious effort of management to enhance productivity. Training of employees is a responsibility of organizations as organizations tend to benefit from the training as the skills and knowledge acquired by employees through training is brought to bear or applied in the course of performing tasks.

Training is normally aimed at developing employee skills, influencing employee’s attitude towards their jobs and the organization and enlightening employees on the operations of the organization, and their expected roles. In Nigerian workers in public sector, it has been observed that workers in public sector hardly trained in their various place of work. The belief that, practice makes perfect is no long apply in our public sector. This adversely affected the level of productivity in the public sector.

(3) Absence of Participative Management: When there is an absence of participative management, workers would not be productive. Participative management is a decision making process where workers discuss with their supervisors and influence decisions that affect them. It explores the feelings and opinions of workers about their jobs. With the use of participative management, every group is consulted before any change is initiated. Through this system, every worker develops a sense of participation, which results in high productivity.

(4) Poor Compensation of Workers: Compensation packages are reward for performance. They can be in either cash items such as salary, allowances and Christmas bonus or in non-cash items which are call fringe benefits such as giving the workers some items from the organizational in scripted products such as calendars, cups, wall

clocks, and among others. The absence of salary increases or bonuses can be a strong de-motivator, primarily because people use money as a scorecard to measure their achievement.

Money is also an indicator to the person of how important he or she is perceived to be within the public sector organization. The absence of salary increases or bonuses to some employees would indicate that they are not valued within the organization. If employees go for more than one year without receiving a raise or a bonus, their productivity is likely to decline, and valuable employees may be tempted to look for other employment, which can be costly in rehiring expenses. When there is poor compensation of workers, the workers will not put in their best in their jobs thereby causing low productivity.

(5) Wrong Choice in Delegation: Delegation is an organizational process that permits the transfer of authority from a superior to a subordinate to make commitments, use resources and take action in relation to duties assigned to him. No government can function well and effectively without delegation. Therefore, when wrong people or workers are delegated, this will drastically affect the anticipated results which consequently will be detrimental to the level of productivity.

(6) Poor communication of the Leaders: The flow of information in a company can be a powerful tool in motivating its workforce. Communication of clearly stated goals and paths to achievement is the best way to begin developing employee talent (Nelson, 2017). Registering and acting on the communication of employees also gives a powerful message about their value to the company and management (Nelson, 2017). Employees want their company and team to succeed; and when management uses the input to help them be productive, a sense of empowerment and ownership of the process develops. The open communication also gives a measure of control over their work environment and allows for the improvement of each individual working situation. The reward employees receive for communicating is not always what managers might view as an award. As Matejka (2021) says, “giving an employee something pleasant is not the only way to reward. You are also rewarding (making life more pleasant) when you take something away that the employee dislikes”.

Enhancing the work life, thereby compensating the employee for the communication, is a way to build rapport and loyalty. When the work environment is pleasant, the employee’s satisfaction and motivation increase. Communication also gives rise to trust between the supervisors and their staff. Trust enables management to give autonomy and to encourage independence, and that trust builds a strong sense of community for the employee. But this is the major problem in Nigerian public sector which leads to low productivity in any sector. There is low flow of communication between the top management and the subordinate which most often weakens the moral of workers’ productivity.

Physical Factors that Affect Labour productivity

Physical factors include: the physical working conditions such as: the lighting, ventilation, noise, cleaner, and furniture arrangement, technical assistance and equipment in the workplace (Dawalibi, 2018). Attention to know the impact of the physical environment on the labour Productivity, as a result of its impact on their acceptance of the work environment and the satisfaction and behaviour. the International Labour Office (2024), indicates low productivity of workers in the medium and small enterprises in developing countries, Because of poor physical

working conditions in the workplace and occupational safety and health facilities. While study of Rahman and Majeed (2022), in Iraq, indicted statistically significant differences between the physical work and improving productivity. The study of Hameed and Amjad (2019) concluded to strong correlation between workplace design and productivity, and that 58% of the variation in employee productivity due to the design of the work environment. Results of the study Hoskins (2006) indicates that 90% of the senior officials noted that the design of the workplace is important to them and affect their productivity, and expected to increase in the employee's performance up to 22%, if their offices are designed well

On the other hand International standards (ISO) indicated the importance of the technical factors in the physical environment of in work which include machinery, equipment, tools, devices, and everything physical which contribute to the production process, as well as the appropriate the physical work specifications with the work designed and the characteristics of individuals to increase productivity (Rahman, and Majeed ,2022). Also Sutermeister provided and discussed many technical factors affecting on the labour productivity, namely: the quality of machinery and equipment, the design of production processes the quality of raw materials, and the work methods (HSP Case Services, 1980). Kukoleca (2022) believe that the characteristic of products and raw materials, the process and the volume of production, work organization the most important technical factors affecting on the labour productivity. Also Arab Labour Organization (2020) indicated many technical factors and technological such as: the degree of integration in production, the rate of capacity utilization, quality and suitability of raw materials and the regularity of its flow, subdivision of production processes, the balance of the production line, the multiplicity of machinery systems, maintenance, the quality of production machines and tools and ease of access to and circulation among workers.

Also a number of researchers believe that the development of technology and equipment has contributed to renew, change production methods, and improve the performance of the technique of production; which leads to raise the effectiveness of labour productivity (Bin Ateg and Hjmaoa, 2022) believes that the modern technology applications changed the various processes associated with manufacturing, led to the changing demand structure of the workforce, " owns the modern experience and skill, especially in automated processes. Hasan, and Abed (2018) notes that the process of the transfer of modern technology to factories in of developing countries is not easy and must make sure that the suitability of the environment, the behavioral patterns, and compatibility with the size of the project and the demand for products.

There were several empirical studies in technical factors such as Schmenner (2025) indicated many factors affecting labour productivity namely: the appropriate use of automation, link production, materials, equipment with control systems, and reduce costs. The results of the study Jarkas, and Bitar (2022) in Kuwait found that the top affecting factors are: Material availability, tool availability, work redone, and Overcrowded work areas. The results of the study Saranga, and Banker (2020) in pharmaceutical industrial sector in India indicates the significant improvement of technological changes which led to an improvement in the productivity of energy efficiency. Also study of Joshi and Singh (2020), in clothes manufacture in Indian concluded to achieved an overall growth in productivity by about 1.7% as a result of the change of technical competence. The results of

the study Goher et al. (2020) specified the most important reasons that lead to low productivity namely : wasting time, unsuitable organization of departments and places of production facilities, lack of clear standards for preforms. on the other hand, many studies have focused on studying the impact of technology on productivity, Jenab (2015) study, reached to the importance of using computers to control and exchange of information for the production process to increase productivity, and that the choice of technology depends on competitive, operational strategies. Also there were many challenges in using new technology in Saudi Arabia, including: the high cost of equipment, loans, integrating new technologies, maintenance, and the scarcity of qualified workforce, training in advanced technologies. Also the results of Sarwar (2012) pointed achieved very low levels of labour productivity and due to low investment in technology in the automobile industry in Pakistan Kaming (2021) studied factors affecting productivity of craftsmen in Indonesia; they found that the top affecting factors are: lack of materials, rework, work interference, absenteeism; lack of equipment, and tools.

Empirical Literature

Ansari (2019) considered quality of work life, empowerment of employees, and incentive system, as organizational factors affecting the improvement of labor productivity. Stated that organizational elements, organizational culture, staff training, service compensation system, organizational structure, employee involvement, selection of personnel, and leadership style have a direct impact on the degree of leadership success. Khaghani (2016) have considered the creation, maintains, and increase in the degree of motivation, as the most important approaches used in labor productivity.

Broumad (2023), in their scientific investigations, have stated that organizational structure is an important factor in the productivity of labor. In his study, pointed out factors such as training, motivation, participation, and implementation of proper management, and proved that they have a direct relationship with improvement in productivity. The empowerment of employees as an important issue in human resource management in organizations, and they also considered finding the individual abilities of employers as an important and strategic element and have tried to improve human resource empowerment factors.

Rayt (2022) concluded that culture plays an effective role in the increase of employee motivations and productivity. Educated people can perform better in terms of productivity and that is why training accelerates the technology diffusion process. High level trainings reduce the degree of investment uncertainty in creativity through increasing the likelihood of successful technological adjustments and consequently increases the amount of these investments. Therefore, it can elevate the level of production and productivity.

Zeynep (2021) in their investigation have mentioned the organizational culture as an important factor in human resource management and also indicate a significant relationship regarding this topic. Employee involvement, and proper training, as effective factors in labor productivity motivation as an important factor. Barne (2016), in his study, investigated organizational culture and mentioned it as a competitive advantage in labor productivity. Organizational structure as an important and effective factor in the increase in labor productivity performance. The effect of organizational culture on labor productivity as very important and essential.

The basic role of the civil servant according to Eme and Andrew (2021), is therefore, to initiate and take active part in all the processes leading to the formulation of policy; and thereafter ensure that the policy agreed by government is faithfully and honestly executed. From this brief statement of the function of the civil servant, it will be seen that the civil service is about the most important single institution affecting the lives of the citizens of a state; its influence is all pervasive, more so in the modern world where most states carry out wide functions in providing social services and regulating the economic life of their citizens.

Obiajulu and Obi (2023) observe that the critical highlight in the major function of the civil service is the implementation of government policies. Civil servants are not policy makers and are not really in a position to question government policies. Whenever a policy is made, it becomes the role of the civil servants to implement the policy the way the government of the day wants it to be.

Also, Ezeani (2025) noted that the civil service is a store of knowledge of past government decisions and procedures. Thus, it plays an educative role by assisting professionals and military political executives (as is the case in Nigeria), especially the new ones to adapt themselves to the realities of their offices. The federal and state civil servants play an important role in policy formulation and advice. They play a major economic, social and educational objective of both the federal and state governments. Furthermore, the civil service also gathers statistical information for the activities of the government. Senior civil servants also have to inform the public about the achievements, abilities and problems facing the government.

Drawing from studies conducted by other researchers, several factors are suggested as possible contributors to the poor performance of organizations in general. Ochola and Ngige (2002) portrays employee satisfaction and motivation as major influences on employee performance in general. The two go further to reveal that job enrichment factors such as challenge, achievement, recognition and responsibility are the real motivators. However, Mullins (1996) argues that, giving people a feedback on their job performance preferably before the supervisor gets it, involving workers in the analysis and change of physical aspects of work environment such as office layout or plant temperature, lighting and cleanliness leads to positive and improved performance in organizations.

Research Design

For this study, the research design adopted is the Ex Post Facto. The Ex Post Facto design was used because the study is a quasi-experimental study examining how independent variables affect a dependent variable.

Theoretical Framework

The new growth theory of Paul Romer (2020) is the best suited theory for this study. The new growth theory is based on the assumption that the production function is not affected only by labor and capital but also by education, improving the quality of labor and capital, better infrastructure which are unaffected by exogenous but endogenous. This means that the growth of education and upgrading skills operate as a multiplier which makes for faster economic growth.

Model Specification

This study shall build a multiple regression model and make use of econometrics procedure in estimating the relationship between my economic variables

The fundamental relationships between the dependent variable and independent variables are specified as follows:

The functional form of the model is specified as:

$$RGDP = f(GEE, GEH) \quad (3.1)$$

The mathematical form of the model is specified as:

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GEE_t + \beta_2 GEH_t \quad (3.2)$$

This econometric form of the model is specified as:

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GEE_t + \beta_2 GEH_t + \mu_t \quad (3.3)$$
$$\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0$$

Where

RGDP= Real Gross Domestic

f= functional relationship

GEE= Government expenditure on education

GEH = Government expenditure on health

β_0 = Constant

β_1, β_2 are the relative slope coefficients and partial elasticity of the parameters.

μ_t = stochastic error term

Granger Causality Test: Although regression analysis deals with the dependence of one variable on the other, it does not necessarily imply causation. In other words, the existence of a relationship between variables does not prove causality or the direction of influence (Gujarati, 2004). The essence of causality analysis, using the granger causality test, is to actually ascertain whether a causal relationship exists between two variables of interest. Below is the Granger specification model:

$$RGDP_t = B_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} B_1 GEE_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^{i=n} B_2 GEH_{t-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{i=n} B_3 RGDP_{t-3} + \mu_{t1} \dots 3.4$$

$$GEE_t = \lambda_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{i=p} \lambda_1 GEE_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^{i=p} \lambda_2 GEH_{t-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{i=p} \lambda_3 RGDP_{t-3} + \mu_{t2} \dots 3.5$$

$$GEH_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{k=i} \alpha_1 GEH_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^{k=i} \alpha_2 GEE_{t-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{k=i} \alpha_3 RGDP_{t-3} + \mu_{t3} \dots 3.6$$

Decision Rule:

If the probability value is less than 0.05, the alternative hypothesis is accepted otherwise the null hypothesis is accepted.

Data Required and Sources

The data required for this study are secondary time series data on government expenditure on education (GEE) government expenditure on health (GEH) and real gross domestic product (RGDP) ranging from 1980-2016. The data employed in this study were obtained from the publications of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), particularly the 2016 statistical Bulletin, Annual report and other official publications.

Unit Root Test Results

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) was used to test for the unit root in the individual variable. The test was done based on the following hypothesis;

The results from the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for unit root are summarized below.

ADF Test for Unit Root

VARIABLES	ADF test Statistics	5% critical Value	Order of Integration
RGDP	-16.41948	-1.950394	I(1)
GEE	-4.473451	-3.587527	I(1)
GEH	-4.693641	-3.544284	I(1)

In the unit root test result table above, all the variables- Real Gross Domestic Product, government education expenditure and government health expenditure are not stationary at order one, that is, they are integrated at order one; I (1).

Since the entire variables are non-stationary at level form, there is need to conduct a co-integration test.

Co-integration Test Result

To test for co-integration among the variables, we will carry out ADF test on the regression residuals as proposed by Gujarati (2004). The ADF unit root test on the residuals work with the same decision rule as unit root test.

The co-integration test result is summarized as follows:

Co-integration Test Result

ADF VALUE	CRITICAL 5% VALUE	TEST RESULT
-7.810725	-3.544284	CO-INTEGRATED

In the co-integration test result above, the ADF test statistics (-7.810725) is greater than the 5% critical value (-3.544284) in absolute terms. This implies that the residuals are stationary (i.e. the variables are co-integrated or that the linear influence of the independent variables cancels out).

Error Correction Mechanism Result

ECM Test Result

Dependent Variable: LOG(RGDP)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/30/25 Time: 09:18

Sample (adjusted): 1999 2024

Included observations: 25 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	13.06639	0.145570	89.76034	0.0000
D(GEE)	1.656045	10.12133	4.163619	0.0010

D(GEH)	1.037739	1.974467	5.525579	0.0026
ECT(-1)	-0.227007	8.500008	-0.671114	0.0118
R-squared	0.596090	Mean dependent var		13.13883
Adjusted R-squared	0.580724	S.D. dependent var		0.783368
S.E. of regression	0.734562	Akaike info criterion		2.325356
Sum squared resid	17.26662	Schwarz criterion		2.501302
Log likelihood	-37.85640	Hannan-Quinn criter.		2.386766
F-statistic	8.601822	Durbin-Watson stat		0.139863
Prob(F-statistic)	0.009073			

In the Error correction mechanism test result above, the magnitude of the short run disparity is -0.227007, that is to say the degree of the short run dynamics is 22.7007. This shows a relatively low speed of adjustment to equilibrium after a shock

Regression Result

Dependent Variable: LOG(RGDP)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/30/25 Time: 09:18

Sample (adjusted): 1999 2024

Included observations: 25 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	13.06639	0.145570	89.76034	0.0000
D(GEE)	1.656045	10.12133	4.163619	0.0010
D(GEH)	1.037739	1.974467	5.525579	0.0026
ECT(-1)	-0.227007	8.500008	-0.671114	0.0118
R-squared	0.596090	Mean dependent var		13.13883
Adjusted R-squared	0.580724	S.D. dependent var		0.783368
S.E. of regression	0.734562	Akaike info criterion		2.325356
Sum squared resid	17.26662	Schwarz criterion		2.501302
Log likelihood	-37.85640	Hannan-Quinn criter.		2.386766
F-statistic	8.601822	Durbin-Watson stat		0.139863
Prob(F-statistic)	0.009073			

In conducting the regression analysis, the variables under consideration are real gross domestic product as the dependent variable while government health expenditure and government education expenditure as the independent variables. From the result the estimated coefficient value of b_0 , b_1 and b_2 , are 13.06639, 1.656045 and 1.037739, respectively. The RGDP values were logged as a result of high coefficients gotten from partial regression.

Result of A prior Test:

VARIABLES	EXPECTED SIGNS	OBSERVED SIGNS	RESULTS
GEE	+VE	+VE	CWES
GEH	+VE	+VE	CWES

CWES – conform with expected sign

Evaluation of Regression Results

Evaluation Based on Economic Criterion

In this subsection is the regression results is been evaluate based on a priori expectations. The signs and magnitude of each variable coefficient is evaluated against theoretical expectations.

The signs of the entire variables coefficient are exactly in line with prior expectations.

The constant term is estimated at 13.06639, this means the model passes through the point 13.06639 mechanically and if the government education expenditure and government expenditure on health are equal to zero, Real Gross Domestic Product would be 13.06639.

The estimated coefficient for Government education expenditure is 1.656045 meaning that if other variables affecting Real Gross Domestic Product are held constant, a unit increase in Government education expenditure will bring about a 1.656045 increase in Real Gross Domestic Product on the average. Likewise, the estimated coefficient of government expenditure on health is 1.037739, meaning that holding all other variables affecting Real Gross Domestic Product constant, a unit increase in government expenditure on health will bring about a 1.037739 increase in Real Gross Domestic Product.

Evaluation Based On Statistical Criterion

This subsection applies the R^2 , the t-test and the f-test to determine the statistical reliability of the estimated parameters. These tests are performed as follows;

R^2 –Result and Interpretation

The coefficient of determination R^2 from the regression result, the R^2 is given as 0.596090 this implies that 59.6090% of the variation in Real Gross Domestic Product is being explained by the variation in Government education expenditure and government expenditure on health

t–Test Result and Interpretation

From the distribution table, $t_{0.025,36} = 2.042$

The result of the t-test of significance is shown in table 4.5 below:

The result of the t-test is presented below and evaluated based on the critical value (2.042) and the value of calculated t-statistics for each variable.

Result of t-Test of Significance

VARIABLES	t-computed (t*)	t-tabulated (t _{a/2})	Conclusion
GEE	4.163619	2.042	Significant
GEH	5.525579	2.042	Significant

Significant (Reject H₀; accept H₁),

Insignificant (Accept H₀).

From the t- test result above,

For Government education expenditure, $t^* > t_{a/2}$, therefore we reject the null hypothesis. Hence Government education expenditure is statistically significant thus Government education expenditure has significant impact on economic growth.

For Government expenditure on health, $t^* > t_{a/2}$ therefore we reject null hypothesis. Hence Government expenditure on health is statistically significant thus Government expenditure on health has significant impact on economic growth.

Result and Interpretation of F-Test of Significance

$v_1=3-1=2$, $V_2=36-3=33$, $df=(2,33)$ at 5% level of significance and $df=(2,33)$, $f_{0.05}= 3.30$ and $F^*=8.601822$.

Result of f-Test of Significance:

Computed f-ratio value	Critical f-ratio value	Result
8.601822	3.30	Statistically significant

Since $f^* > f_{0.05}$, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the variables Government education expenditure and Government expenditure on health have joint inference on economic growth of Nigeria. This implies that the entire regression plain is insignificant.

Evaluation Based on Econometric Criterion

In this subsection, the following econometric test is used to evaluate the result obtained from our model: autocorrelation, normality, granger causality test.

Result and Interpretation of Autocorrelation Test

Using the durbin-watson statistics, the region of no autocorrelation (positive or negative) is given as follows

$$du < d^* < (4-du)$$

$$du = 1.58$$

$$d^* = 0.139863$$

$$(4-du) = 4 - 1.58 = 2.42$$

By substitution, the region becomes:

$$1.58 > 0.139863 < 2.42$$

The result shows that there is presence of autocorrelation problem in the model as the computed durbin Watson statistics did not fall within the zero autocorrelation regions.

Normality Test

Result of Normality Test

The probability values shows that it is less than 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted which means that the residuals of the regressed variables are not normally distributed.

4.2.3.3 Granger Causality Test: Result and Interpretation

The essence of causality analysis, using the granger causality test, is to actually ascertain whether a causal relationship exists between two variables of interest.

The result of the normality test indicates that probability value of the test statistics is less than 0.05 level of significance, hence giving us the choice to reject the null hypotheses. Therefore, the residuals are not normally distribution.

Result of Causality Test:

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 10/30/25 Time: 03:44

Sample: 1999 2024

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
GEE does not Granger Cause RGDP	36	72.8621	2.E-12
RGDP does not Granger Cause GEE		2.36643	0.1105
GEH does not Granger Cause RGDP	36	232.735	2.E-19
RGDP does not Granger Cause GEH		6.28553	0.0051
GEH does not Granger Cause GEE	36	6.21127	0.0054
GEE does not Granger Cause GEH		4.74229	0.0160

The e-views generated granger causality result judging with the probability decision rule, shows a unidirectional causality relationship flowing from government education expenditure exists between government education expenditure and Real Gross Domestic Product also a bidirectional causality relationship exists between government expenditure on health and Real Gross Domestic Product.

Evaluation of Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: from the t-Test result, the null hypothesis is rejected in all the variables based on our t-Test decision rule. Therefore, government expenditure on education and health has significant impact on Economic growth of Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: owing to the regression result, government expenditure on health and government education expenditure both has positive relationship with real gross domestic product; we therefore accept the alternative hypothesis which states that human capital development has a relationship with economic growth.

Hypothesis Three: from the Granger Causality Result, government expenditure on health and government education expenditure has causality relationship with Real Gross Domestic Product; the alternative hypothesis which says that human capital development has a causality relationship with Economic Growth of Nigeria is therefore accepted.

Implication of the Results

Haven observed in the regression result that government expenditure on health and government education expenditure both has positive relationships with Real Gross Domestic Product over the period covered, it implies that an increase in the values of government expenditure on health and government education expenditure will lead to an increase in the economic growth of Nigeria.

However, the granger causality result indicates a unidirectional causality relationship flowing from government education expenditure exists between government education expenditure and Real Gross Domestic Product, a bidirectional causality relationship exists between government expenditure on health and Real Gross Domestic Product.

This implies that the past values of government education expenditure can be used in forecasting the future values of Real Gross Domestic Product but the past values of Real Gross Domestic Product cannot be used in forecasting the future values of government education expenditure. Moreover, the past values of Real Gross Domestic Product can be used in forecasting the future values of government expenditure on health also the past values of government expenditure on health can be used in forecasting the future values of Real Gross Domestic Product.

Conclusion

Derived from the findings of this study, we therefore conclude that health and education expenditure positively impact on economic growth of Nigeria. We also conclude that variables of human capital development have significant impacts on economic growth in Nigeria Finally, we conclude that there is a causality relationship exists between Human capital development and economic growth in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings above, the following recommendations are suggested

1. It is of importance haven seen the extent to which health and education expenditure impact on the economic growth of Nigeria that the government provide infrastructural facilities both for schools and hospitals so as to ensure that pupils in government schools get quality education in a conducive environment and also good medical care which will help boost the economic growth of the country.
2. The government and its education and health agencies should as well reach out to rural communities in a bid to provide educational and health facilities for the dwellers of such places which will increase the human capital of the country and hence the economic growth of Nigeria.

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